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STEM TO STEAM: INTEGRATING ARTS THROUGH MIND MAPPING STRATEGY FOR STUDENTS' CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING IN SCIENCE

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ABSTRACT

The study utilized a mixed method research design. Quantitative data were gathered using the quasi-one group pre-test-post-test experimental research design using the validated researcher-made instrument name Students Biological Conceptual Understanding Test (SBTU) covering the 6 biology topics for Grade 7. Qualitative data were gathered utilizing the constructivist grounded theory involving constant comparative analysis of data from varied sources. The participants of the study involved the randomly selected 40 Grade 7 STE students of a National High School situated in the Division of Passi City enrolled in the school year 2018-2019. A total of 240 mind maps were created but only 6 mind maps for each topic were taken for analysis. The results of the data analysis revealed that initially, students had an "average" conceptual understanding. The Posttest result showed that participants exposed to mind mapping strategy has improved conceptual understanding from "average" to "high". There was a significant difference in the conceptual understanding of the students prior to and after exposure to mind mapping strategy. Utilizing constructivist grounded theory through constant comparative analysis, students revealed how they understand biological concept. Students further understand biological concepts by provoking their creativity, critical thinking, encouraging collaboration, developing their communication skill.

KEYWORDS: Mind mapping; Conceptual Understanding; Constant Comparative Analysis; Constructivist Grounded Theory

I. INTRODUCTION

For 21st Century solutions to 21st Century problems, the Arts have a vital role in developing a creative mind-set within the STEM areas. Learning Science Technology Engineering Mathematics subjects in a classroom setting isn't always inviting for all learning styles. A wellspring of opinion that combining science and the arts in the form of STEAM education is essential for producing a creative, scientifically literate, and ethically astute citizenry and workforce for the 21st century (Boy, 2013; Edwards, 2010; Feldman, 2015; Piro, 2010). STEAM, an interdisciplinary spin on STEM that includes an "A" for art, is an integral part of influencing kids' interest in STEM by allowing kids to explore these subjects through hands-on making. The true magic of STEAM education is that it allows all students to identify with science, technology, engineering, and mathematics. Transforming learning environments from STEM to STEAM changes the way kids see and think. Art provides the typical STEM classroom new avenues of fun and playful possibilities. Mind Mapping is an effective artistic learning tool that fosters students' creativity and acts as a trigger device for the brain, creating an explosion in creativity, innovation and knowledge sharing. Mirroring the

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constructivist theory, mind mapping is believed to be an effective intervention to improve students' conceptual understanding.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study aimed to determine the effects of mind mapping techniques on Grade 7 Science Technology and Engineering students' conceptual understanding in Biology, specifically the study sought to answer to the following specific concerns: What is the conceptual understanding of the students prior to and after exposure to the mind mapping strategy? Is there a significant difference in the conceptual understanding of the students prior to and after exposure to the mind mapping strategy? How do students understand biological concepts through mind mapping? What assertions can be postulated by integrating Arts in STEM? The study utilized a mixed method research design. Quantitative data were gathered using the quasi- one group pre-test-post-test experimental research design using the validated researcher-made instrument name Students Biological Conceptual Understanding Test (SBTU) covering the 6 biology topics for Grade 7. Qualitative data were gathered utilizing the constructivist grounded theory involving constant comparative analysis of data from varied sources such as: interview transcripts, students' mind maps and written journals. The participants of the study involved the randomly selected 40 Grade 7 STE students of a National High School situated in the Division of Passi City enrolled in the school year 2018-2019. Six students were tagged after the pre-test, 2 with the highest test score, 2 for the average and 2 students with the lowest Score. 36 students were chosen at random for the interview. Experimental period lasted for six weeks. Students were asked to make mind map for each lesson. The mind maps created were used as an instrument to understand and analysed their conceptual understanding of the lesson. All in all there was 240 mind maps created, only the 6 tagged students whose mind maps for every lesson were taken for qualitative analysis. The data analysis involved quantitative and qualitative data. In quantitative data, results of the SBCU Test were utilized. The data gathered was subjected to appropriate statistical analysis using the SPSS Program. In the qualitative part of the study as shown in Figure 2, narrative analysis and constant comparative analysis of students' outputs were done including transcribing, coding, writing memos, identifying common themes, supporting and matching themes and writing the manuscript. The result of analysis from each source is interlinked with each other to come-up with themes that eventually led to theory construction.

III. RESULT

Table 1. *Pretest and Posttest Performance*

Category	M	Descriptive Rating	SD
Pretest	15.50	Average	4.013
Posttest	23.75	High	3.311

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Legend: 24.01 - 30.00- Very High; 18.01 - 24.00- High; 12.01 - 18.00- Average; 6.01 - 12.00- Low; 0 - 6.00- Very Low

Table 2. Differences in the Pre-Post Performance

Category	Df	M	t – value	Significance
Pretest	39	15.5	-14.003*	0.000
Posttest		23.75		

* $p < .05$

IV. DISCUSSION

The results of the data analysis as shown in Table 1 revealed that initially, students had an “average” conceptual understanding ($M=15.50$, $SD=4.013$). This simply imply that prior to the intervention mind mapping activity, students have minimal understanding of the selected biological topics. The posttest result showed that participants exposed to mind mapping strategy has improved conceptual understanding from “average” to “high” ($M=23.75$, $SD=3.311$). It also showed that their pretest scores are more dispersed than their posttest scores. This signifies that the use of mind mapping as a form of arts integration in science education improved students’ conceptual understanding. From these results, Arts integration through the utilization of mind mapping improves the conceptual understanding of students. Therefor it is strongly suggested to incorporate art activities for a more meaningful teaching-learning experience and fill the gaps in the curriculum. Mind mapping strategy is very effective in incorporating art in the STEM education and improving students’ conceptual understanding.

To determine whether there was a significant difference in the pre-post treatment of the group, the pre-post scores were subjected to the test of significance at .05 levels using the t – test for correlated means. Table 2 shows that there exist a significant difference between the pretest and posttest conceptual understanding scores of the participants taught using the mind mapping strategy $t(39)=-14.003$, $P=0.000$, the results further validate that mind mapping can positively make a difference in the performance of the student. The intervention definitely improved their conceptual understanding of the selected biology concepts.

Utilizing constructivist grounded theory through constant comparative analysis, students revealed how they understand biological concept. Students’ expressed their journey and perceptions on how they understand biological concepts using mind mapping from their first encounter of the mind map, their making of the mind maps and until such time that they have reached conceptual understanding.

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V. CONCLUSIONS

Students further understand biological concepts by provoking their creativity, critical thinking, encouraging collaboration, developing their communication skill. Mind mapping as a form of arts integration in STEM is very effective in improving students' biological conceptual understanding. Arts must therefore be an integral part of the STEM curriculum to develop a holistic 21st century learner. Overall, mind mapping has its difficulties and challenges but it is incomparable to its numerous benefits and proven effectiveness as explicated by the informants who have experienced doing and using it as a learning technique. Therefore, integrating techniques with a touch of art such as mind mapping effectively assist educators in cultivating a better sense of learning among learners by providing an avenue to learn with ease combined with fun. A paradigm shift from STEM to STEAM is asserted.

Teachers play a great role in developing the skills and abilities of the students. The creative approach and varied activities that stimulate student's curiosity, creativity, collaboration and critical thinking should be given utmost importance.

Early research studies on ground-breaking STEAM curricula in the US have demonstrated that learning activities integrating science, technology and the arts successfully engage minority and disadvantaged students, resulting in improved literacy and numeracy competencies (Clark, 2014; Stoelinga, Silk, Reddy & Rahman, 2015).

Mind mapping strategy was viewed as an artistic tool that can foster students' creativity as well as critical thinking. It acts as a trigger device for your brain, creating an explosion in creativity, innovation and knowledge sharing.

In mapping the mind map, students are encouraged to go beyond the information provided thus through mind mapping students' skills in research and brainstorming is also developed. Also the benefit of using mind maps goes beyond this. Through mind mapping the teacher check on students understanding, correct misconceptions and build on students talents.

The utilization and integration of arts in the STEM must be considered to develop and bridge the gaps in the curriculum. Educators must think of ways to incorporate fun and excitement as well as a taste of challenge in the teaching and learning process. When students are exposed to challenging activities they become more motivated to learn more. Also teaching strategies must be varied to address students multiple intelligences.

Learning is more meaningful when students feel that they are actively involved in the learning process. Likewise it is important for administrators to include arts in any field of discipline that would cater and develop students' innate abilities and talents. Support should be provided to teachers in terms of materials and facilities and should encourage teachers to plan and execute more fun engaging strategies in the classroom.

It is suggested that Biology instruction must not only be a classroom routine, rather, it must include varied activities which stimulates students' learning. It must be avenue for students to express their uniqueness and creativity.

Teachers should provide opportunities for his/her students to actively comprehend the lessons using their preferred learning styles and approaches. Educators must address individual differences and build on students' strengths and developed students' weaknesses. Teaching biology using mind mapping strategy should be included in the daily instruction to enhance students' conceptual understanding. Teachers must also think of other strategies to incorporate the arts to STEM education.

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Since learning Biology is a developmental process, the subject must be taught according to its complexity and difficulty using appropriate strategies and techniques other than mind mapping. Teachers and parents must encourage students to use other learning tools to improve their understanding of the lesson.

Information regarding the effectiveness of mind mapping strategy in teaching Biology needs to be disseminated. Division or district workshop-seminars are recommended by the researcher so that teachers may acquire more knowledge and skills in employing this approach in their classrooms.

Similar studies may be conducted in the future using other grade levels, wider sample size, and using other approaches to further enrich and understand the present investigation.

Administrators and teachers to design instructional materials that will cater to individual student's needs and improve the quality of teaching instruction for students through mind mapping strategy.

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